

Structural, optical, dielectric and ferroelectric properties of nanocrystalline Yb^{+3} doped $\text{Ba}_2\text{NaNb}_5\text{O}_{15}$

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Abstract:

Yb^{+3} doped nanocrystalline of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Na}_{1-3x}\text{Yb}_x\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{15}$ (hereafter BNN- Yb_x , where $x=0, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06$) was synthesized using sol-gel method. The phase conformation of synthesized nano-crystalline powders was conformed through Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. Morphology of the synthesized nanocrystalline materials was conformed through scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Room temperature dielectric constant of BNN- Yb ($x=0.06$) materials show nearly three times higher value than that of undoped $\text{Ba}_2\text{NaNb}_5\text{O}_{15}$ (BNN) at 100 kHz. The improved remnant polarization was also observed for BNN- Yb ($x=0.06$), with compared to that of undoped BNN ceramic.

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Introduction :

Barium sodium niobate, $\text{Ba}_2\text{NaNb}_5\text{O}_{15}$ (BNN) crystal is the tungsten bronze family which belongs to the orthorhombic crystal structure (space group $Pba2$) at room temperature. Over past forty five years immense research is going on this materials because its actuality of applications such as electro-optic, non-linear optic, acousto-optic, ferroelectric, piezoelectric and a few other properties.¹⁻¹⁰ The different physical properties such as melting point (~ 1773 K), refractive index ($n_x=2.373$, $n_y=2.370$ and $n_z=2.256$ at $0.532 \mu\text{m}$), transparency region ($0.4 \mu\text{m}$ to $5 \mu\text{m}$), optical

band gap ($E_g = 3.1$ eV), dielectric constant (i.e., $\epsilon_r = 57$) ferroelectric (i.e., spontaneous polarization value $40 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), piezoelectric properties (i.e., $d_{33} = 37$ and $d_{11} = 42$) and electro-optic coefficient (i.e., $r_{42} = 92 \times 10^{-12}$ m/V) along with Curie temperature or ferroelectric transition temperature (833 K) of BNN crystal is available in the literature.^{3,9, 10} Different authors have grown the single crystals of rare earth (RE) ions doped BNN using a formula $\text{BaNa}_{1-3x}\text{RE}_x\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{15}$ (where RE = Nd^{+3} , Yb^{+3} , Sc^{+3} , Y^{+3} , La^{+3} and Lu^{+3}) and the grown crystals showed a better second harmonic generation (SHG) than that of pure BNN crystals.¹¹⁻¹⁴ In addition, this material is also considered as an interesting host material for luminescent ions. The potential applications for host lattice of laser ions of this material was confirmed through the extensive studies with Ho^{3+} , Yb^{3+} and Tm^{3+} .^{15, 16} The emission properties of different RE ions doped such as Eu^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Sm^{3+} and Dy^{3+} of BNN crystals was also studied and reported in the literature.^{17, 18} Moreover, the foresaid properties of pure and RE doped BNN single crystals were grown above the 1703 K using Czochralski technique. The main disadvantage of this material is especially cracks (due to the large thermal expansion in c axis at near 793-863 K) easily developed during the crystal growth process. The production cost of BNN single crystals is very high and the quality of thin films is also very poor, therefore this material has not yet considered for the industrial applications, even though it shows very attractive application especially in electro-optic application.¹⁹

In contrast to crystal growth, the preparation of ceramic is more superior, because it can be made into larger and more complex parts. A number of different polycrystalline ceramics were well known for their promising piezoelectric, pyroelectric, light emitting diode, solar energy, capacitors and the other related applications.^{20,21} The single phase of BNN ceramic powder was achieved through molten NaCl salt synthesis at 1073 K above 3 hr and the starting

materials were BaCO_3 and Nb_2O_5 .²² *Kundu et al.* prepared BNN nano crystallites embedded in glass matrices²³ and nano polycrystalline material using citrate assisted sol-gel method²⁴ and these powders were demonstrated for the potentialities photoluminescence (PL) applications under ultraviolet excitation source. Moreover, very recently the enhanced piezoelectricity, photoluminescence and up-conversion emissions were observed in the rare earth doped perovskite oxide ($\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$) ferroelectric materials.²⁵ The Er-doped BNN ceramic powder shows the promising candidate for white light phosphor application.²⁶ The objective of the present investigations has been to visualize the effect of the rare-earth *ion* (Yb^{3+}) doping on the electrical properties of BNN nanocrystals. To the best of the knowledge of the authors no literature exists on electrical properties of Yb^{3+} doped BNN polycrystalline ceramic powder samples. Therefore, attempt was made to synthesize fine powders of Yb^{3+} doped BNN via soft-chemistry (sol-gel) route. Because the sol-gel derived fine powders are typically more homogeneous and reactive than those prepared by a conventional solid-state reaction, since the reagents are mixed at the atomic level.²⁷ Hence, in this article, we report the details concerning about the structural, optical, dielectric and ferroelectric properties of Y^{3+} doped BNN nanocrystalline powders.

Materials and Methodology:

To synthesize Yb^{3+} doped BNN nanocrystalline powders, the 99% purity of starting materials, barium nitrate, sodium acetate, ammonium niobate (V) oxalate pentahydrate, ytterbium (III) oxide and anhydrous citric acid were used. The procedure started with the manufacture of the precursor solution of peroxocitro-niobium using a technique akin to what previous researchers have documented.^{24, 26} To do this, 30 millilitres of H_2O_2 were constantly stirred until a suitable quantity of citric acid was dissolved. The aforesaid solution was stirred

vigorously for almost an hour at 343 K after adding the required amount of ammonium niobate (V) oxalate pentahydrate, which produced a clear yellow solution after 30 minutes. Drop by drop, aqueous ammonia was added to the solution to bring its pH up to 6.5 to 7. In a different beaker, the appropriate volumes of citric acid, sodium acetate, and barium nitrate were dissolved in 25 milliliters of deionized water before being gradually added to the above solution. Separately, the required concentrations of ytterbium (III) oxide ($x=0, 0.02, 0.04$ and 0.06) were dissolved in strong nitric acid and added to the solution above while being continuously stirred. Ammonia solution was added to the solution in order to keep its pH within the range of 6.5–7.0. When the temperature was increased to 403 K, water began to evaporate and a thick gel developed. At 573 K, the temperature was increased even further, at which point the gels began to burn and leave a residue. Thus the obtained powder was heat treated at 1023 K/3h to achieve the BNN-Yb_x ($x=0, 0.02, 0.04$ and 0.06) nanocrystalline materials.

Using a PANalytical x-ray diffractometer in the 2θ range of $10\text{--}80^\circ$ with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (1.5408 Å) radiation, x-ray powder diffraction experiments were performed on the samples in order to determine the BNN-Yb_x nanocrystalline phase development. The synthesized powder's crystallite size distribution and shape were examined using a scanning electron microscope (FEI Inspect F50). The software tool Sigma Scan Pro 4.0, created by Jandel Scientific, was utilized to analyse the SEM pictures captured and determine the crystallites' statistical size distribution. The well-separated crystallites were labelled individually for image analysis using a pixel-calibrated scale bar, and a statistical average was then determined. To measure the dielectric and ferroelectric properties, the obtained powder was pressed into pellets of 10mm in diameter using 3% poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) and 1% polyethylene glycol as a binder. To achieve the densification, the cold-pressed pellets were sintered at 1523 K for 3 hours. The densities of the

sintered pellets were measured by the Archimedes principle using xylene as the liquid medium. The polarization (Hysteresis loop) measurements were performed using RT66A Radiant ferroelectric loop tracer. To study dielectric measurements, conducting silver past was painted on the both flat surfaces of the specimens followed by curing of the silver electrode at 200 °C/10h. The capacitance of the specimens with silver electrode were measured as a function of frequency (100Hz–1MHz) using an impedance gain-phase analyzer (HP4194A) at room temperature.

Results and discussion:

X-ray powder diffraction pattern of BNN-Yb_x (x=0, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06) nanocrystalline materials obtained at 1023 K/3h were depicted in Figure 1. For the comparison purpose, the ICSD (PDF no. 01-086-0739) data of BNN sample is also included in the same figure. Here all XRD diffraction peaks of synthesized samples were exactly matched with the ICSD data of BNN phase. This indicates that Yb³⁺ had been incorporated into the BNN lattice. Furthermore the size of nanoparticles for each sample was also calculated using the Debye-Scherrer equation with help of XRD pattern. The calculated particle sizes were 178 nm, 146 nm, 125 nm and 113 nm for x=0, 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 respectively.

Figure 1: XRD pattern of ICSD data of BNN and BNN-Yb_x nanocrystalline materials.

The BNN-Yb_x nanocrystalline samples were subjected to SEM image analysis in order to visualise the crystallite and its shape. Figure 2 (a-d) depicts the representative morphology of BNN-Yb_x, which was calcined at 1023 K/3h. Here the decrease of crystallite with increase of Yb³⁺ concentration in the BNN sample was observed. The average crystallite size was found to be 220 nm, 203 nm, 198 nm and 181 nm for x=0, 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 samples respectively.

Figure 2: SEM images of BNN-Yb_x nanocrystalline materials.

Figure 3: Optical diffused reflection spectra of BNN-Yb_x nanocrystalline materials.

Diffuse reflectance spectra of the synthesised samples were obtained in the 250–1000 nm wavelength range in order to assess their optical band gap. Figure 3 displays the recorded spectra for the BNN-Yb_x (x=0, 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06) samples that were calcined at 1023 K/2h. For every sample, a distinct cut-off at 342 nm was noted. The reflection spectra showed certain dips at various wavelength positions, which correspond to the absorption bands of the Yb³⁺ ions in the sample. The change from 4I_{15/2} to 4G_{11/2} is responsible for the band at 377 nm. Using the diffuse reflectance spectra, we estimated the optical band gap of the each material with the help of Kubelka–Munk function. The obtained optical band gap were found to be 3.12, 3.17, 3.25 and 3.35 eV for x=0, 0.02, 0.04 and 0.06 samples respectively.

The densities of the sintered pellets were measured by the Archimedes principle using xylene as the liquid medium. The measured densities for each sample are tabulated in Table 1. The highest density where x=0.04 was observed in Yb³⁺ doped BNN ceramic.

The dielectric and ferroelectric properties can be improve by doping of rare earth elements, and these things were observed in rare earth doped Na_{0.5}Bi_{0.5}TiO₃ (NBT) ceramic.^{27, 28} In order to understand the effects on electrical properties of Yb³⁺ doped BNN, the room temperature electrical properties were carried out. The variation of dielectric constant and loss tangent as a function of frequency of Yb³⁺ doped BNN ceramic was depicted in Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively. The dielectric constant and loss tangent of each sample at 100 kHz is tabulated in Table 1. However, at the same frequency the dielectric constant and tangent loss of pure BNN ceramic were 70 and 0.024 respectively.²⁹ The highest dielectric constant rare Yb³⁺ doped BNN, especially x=0.06, is attribute to higher density of the ceramic.

Figure 4: Room temperature dielectric constant of BNN-Yb_x pellets sintered at 1523 K/3h

Figure 5: Room temperature dielectric loss of BNN-Yb_x pellets sintered at 1523 K/3h

Ferroelectric (P versus E) hysteresis loops of the BNN-Yb_x ceramic pellets were also measured, and the measured hysteresis loops are depicted in Figure 6. A significant enhancement in remnant polarization (P_s) was observed in Yb³⁺-doped BNN ceramic when compared to that of pure BNN ceramic. A comparison of the ferroelectric parameters of the each sample is given in the Table 1.

Figure 6: Room temperature ferroelectric hysteresis loop of BNN-Yb_x pellets sintered at 1523 K/3h

Table 1. The values of density, dielectric constant (ϵ_r') and loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) measured at 100 kHz, Remnant Polarization ($2P_r$) and Coercive Field ($2E_c$) of sintered pellets at 1523 K/3h for BNN- Yb_x samples (All the parameters were measured at room temperature).

Physical properties	BNN-Yb _x			
	x=0	x=0.02	x=0.04	x=0.06
Density (gm/cc)	4.98	5.11	5.14	5.16
ϵ_r' at 100 kHz	72	192	275	291
$\tan \delta$	0.024	0.048	0.061	0.068
$2P_r$ ($\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$)	0.3	0.633	1.16	1.28
$2E_c$ (kV/cm)	9.6	14.34	23.79	17.36

Conclusions:

Yb³⁺ doped BNN nanocrystalline material was synthesized via citrate assisted sol gel method, and the phase conformation studies were carried out. The improved dielectric constant at 100 kHz of Yb³⁺ doped BNN (where x=0.06) was observed. The highest remnant polarization was also observed in Yb³⁺ doped BNN ceramic samples. Hence the improved dielectric and ferroelectric properties of rare earth doped BNN-Yb_x (where x=0.06) is a good candidate for the ferroelectric and dielectric application point of view.

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